

CRYPTO-SECURITIES AND THE *LEX REI SITAE* RULE

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The progressive implementation of distributed ledger technologies (DLT) in finance has reached a large number of areas, including the registration of securities. Although limited to non-listed corporations, DLT has become in some jurisdictions an alternative to the traditional securities registration in physical certificates or book-entry form. In addition, as a way of obtaining finance, new instruments are being issued in initial coin offerings (ICOs) –hence registered in tokenized form-, which may also qualify as securities under the applicable regulatory rules.

Legal systems are struggling to accommodate the different dimensions of DLT in the substantive-law level. Possibly the most controversial area is the rights in rem over such crypto-securities. Unsurprisingly, whether or not the crypto holders have a proprietary claim becomes key in a number of situations and the answer varies largely across jurisdictions and indeed is yet unclear in most of them.

If we accept a proprietary characterization of these claims, the choice of law rule, widely recognized in comparative law, is *lex rei sitae*, i.e. the law applicable is the law of the place where the crypto-asset is located. Of course, the application of such rule is problematic with any intangible, as shown with the case of securities registered in book-entry form and held with an intermediary.

In the EU, harmonized conflict-of-laws rules on book-entry securities solved the problem by following the so-called PRIMA approach (place of the relevant intermediary account, i.e. a *conto*

sitae rule) (e.g. Directive 2002/47/EC on financial collateral arrangements).

The 2006 Hague Securities Convention addressed similar issues with a slightly different approach. It establishes a primary rule based on the law chosen for the account agreement, if the relevant intermediary has, at the time of the agreement, an office in that State. As the 2006 Hague Securities Convention shows, in the case of choice of law rules for proprietary aspects in intangible assets (intermediated securities) it is accepted to depart from the *situs* as connecting factor.

The location problem is further exacerbated in the case of crypto-securities. On the one hand, DLT replaces central registers with a ledger which is entirely distributed among all nodes. On the other hand, the network is disintermediated and therefore there is no “relevant” account in the sense of the PRIMA rule. In order to solve the problem, a number of connecting factors have been proposed for a new choice of law rule, many of them somehow inspired in the PRIMA rule. Others rather seek an analogy with choice of law rules for non-intermediated securities.

Even if there is no perfect solution, this last approach, which needs to be further explored, is arguably the best option consistent with the technology neutrality principle and which provides a foreseeable solution which accords with parties’ expectations.